

Building Trustworthy Repositories: Introduction to CoreTrustSeal Certification

Online Workshop

DARIAH Virtual Annual Event 2020

Wednesday October 14 14:00 – 15:30

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KNAW Humanities Cluster/CLARIN ERIC

Program of the workshop

	Title	Duration	Presenter
01	Introduction + Mentimeter	15 minutes	Tomasz / René
02	CoreTrustSeal – short introduction Q&A	15 minutes	René
03	CTS repositories and FAIR data objects Q&A	15 minutes	Birger
04	Use case 1: CTS in CLARIN Q&A	15 minutes	Daan
05	Use case 2: CTS in CESSDA Q&A	15 minutes	Birger
06	Discussion / Conclusion + Mentimeter	15 minutes	René / Tomasz

Project:

SSHOC

social sciences & humanities open cloud

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Objectives:

- Creating the social sciences and humanities (**SSH**) part of European Open Science Cloud (**EOSC**)
- Maximising **re-use** through **Open Science** and **FAIR** principles (standards, common catalogue, access control, semantic techniques, training)
- Interconnecting existing and new infrastructures (clustered cloud infrastructure)
- Establishing appropriate **governance model** for SSH-EOSC

General information:

- RIA, 47 partners, 40 months duration (01.2019-04.2022), ~14M EUR budget
- Project website: www.SSHOpenCloud.eu

SSHOC and CoreTrustSeal

WP8 Governance, Sustainability and Quality Assurance

- Task 8.2 Trust & Quality Assurance
 - Training and outreach on CoreTrustSeal
 - CoreTrustSeal Support Program for repositories
 - 14 repositories selected

CoreTrustSeal and Scholarly primitives

- Scholarly primitives are well supported by repositories
- But how can you demonstrate trustworthiness?
- One of the answers is to follow agreed basic rules such as those defined by CoreTrustSeal

menti.com

Mentimeter

Please enter the code

Submit

The code is found on the screen in front of you